

STRUCTURE-PROPERTY RELATIONSHIPS OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

The structure-property relationships of composite sandwich panels of KEVLAR* aramid and graphite have been investigated. These composite sandwich panels, consisting of either facesheet materials of KEVLAR 49* or graphite fabric and four different densities of poly (vinyl chloride) (PVC) foam cores, demonstrate exceptional modulus-to-weight-ratios, strength-to-weight ratios, and low-energy impact resistance. The macroscopic and microscopic failure modes, energy absorbing characteristics, and flexural mechanical properties were examined as functions of the constituent material properties. The effects of low-velocity impact on these composite sandwich panels were studied by using instrumented impact testing. Scanning electron microscopy was employed to identify the microscopic failure mechanisms. The flexural mechanical properties were obtained by three-point flexural testing. The impact failure mechanism of these sandwich panels was changed from facesheet-dominated to foam-core-dominated behavior, when the density of the PVC foam core increases from low density to relatively high density. The flexural modulus and strength of these sandwich panels increase tremendously as the density of the foam core increases.

INTRODUCTION

Composite sandwich panels offer exceptional flexural stiffness to weight ratios compared to that of the facesheets alone when not bonded to the foam core material. If we define, R_b , which is the ratio of the equivalent bending stiffness to weight ratio of the composite sandwich panel to the stiffness to weight ratio of the composite of the same amount of facesheet material, then

$$R_b = \frac{(E_f(3ah^2 + 3a^2h + a^3) + E_c h^3)d_f}{E_f a^2(ad_f + hd_c)} \quad (1)$$

Where E_c and E_f are the moduli of the core and facesheet, respectively. d_c and d_f are the densities of the core and facesheet, respectively. h and $a/2$ are the thicknesses of the core and facesheet, respectively. If $E_f \gg E_c$ and $h \gg a$, then Equation (1) can be simplified to¹

$$R_b = \frac{3h^2 d_f}{a(ad_f + hd_c)} \quad (2)$$

For a typical composite sandwich panel, $h = 10a$ and $d_f = 5d_c$, the value of R_b is 100 from Equation (2). This means that the equivalent bending stiffness of a composite sandwich panel is about 100 times compared to the

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composite containing the same amount of facesheet material which is not bonded to the core material. However, the equivalent tensile stiffness is not the case. If we apply the similar definition for the ratio of specific equivalent tensile stiffness, R_t , then

$$R_t = \frac{(aE_f + hE_c)d_f}{E_f(ad_f + hd_c)} \quad (3)$$

If $E_f \gg E_c$, then Equation (3) becomes

$$R_t = \frac{ad_f}{ad_f + hd_c} \quad (4)$$

For a typical composite sandwich panel, $h = 10a$ and $d_f = 5d_c$, the value of R_t is only 1/3 from Equation (4). This means that the equivalent tensile stiffness of composite sandwich panels actually decreases compared to the same amount of facesheet as a composite. Therefore, we can conclude that the major advantages for using a composite sandwich panel are the flexural and impact properties instead of tensile properties. This is a distinct feature of composite sandwich panels compared to traditional fibrous composites.

The impact response of various composite sandwich panels has been investigated in our previous publication². Presented here are impact and flexural properties of two composite sandwich panels containing the high performance KEVLAR 49* aramid and graphite fabrics as facesheet materials bonded to PVC foam cores with four different densities.

EXPERIMENTAL

The facesheet materials were plain-woven KEVLAR 49 fabrics (woven by Burlington) and graphite fabrics (Hercules AW193P). The core materials were 12.7 mm thick Klegecell rigid PVC foam (by Klegecell Polimex) with a variety of approximate densities of 45, 55, 75, and 240 Kg/m³ (designated as PVC-45, 55, 75, and 240). The facesheet fabrics were impregnated with an epoxy resin (mixture of Ciba Geigy 507 and 956, mixing ratio 4:1 by weight), and then bonded to the core materials using the same epoxy as an adhesive. The whole sandwich (220 mm x 220 mm) was cured and formed by using compression molding at minimal pressure (50 lbs.) and 60°C for 45 min. The nominal specimen dimensions for instrumented impact testing (Dynatup model 730) were 100 mm x 100 mm x 14 mm. For three-point-bending test (Instron model 1125), the nominal specimen sizes were 100 mm x 13 mm x 14 mm with a 50 mm test span. SEM was employed to identify the fracture mechanisms of the composite sandwich panels.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Instrumented Impact Testing

Figure 1 illustrates the load-time traces of the facesheets of KEVLAR and Graphite when the facesheets are not bonded to any core material. Both specimens were penetrated and demonstrated the same value of max. load (about .3 kn). The corresponding load-time traces of four different PVC cores (PVC-45, 55, 75, and 240) are shown in Fig. 2. The max. load increases as the density of the PVC core increases. Especially, when the density increases three times from PVC-75 to PVC-240, the value of max. load increases more than eight times.

Fig. 3 shows the impact response of the sandwich panels (KEVLAR/PVC/KEVLAR) of KEVLAR. Doublet behavior on the load-time traces was observed for those composite sandwich panels containing low-density PVC such as PVC-45, 55, and

75. The doublet in the load-time trace corresponds to failure of the top facesheet and the back facesheet, respectively. The valley between two peaks corresponds to the penetration of the low-density foam core. The energy absorbed by the low-density core material is small and is assumed to be approximately the same for each of the facesheets³. Since the load-time traces for KEVLAR/PVC-45, 55, and 75 are about the same, the impact response of all these sandwich panels are facesheet-dominated and the contribution from the foam core is negligible. However, the doublet behavior of load-time trace of the high-density-core sandwich panels, KEVLAR/PVC-240, is not as clear as the behavior in low-density-core panels. Meanwhile, there are several orders of magnitude increase in max. load and total absorbed energy of sandwich panels of KEVLAR, if the high density foam core, PVC-240, is used. The mechanisms of impact failure have switched from facesheet-dominated event to foam-core-dominated event.

The impact response of the graphite sandwich panels (Gr/PVC/Gr) is illustrated in Fig. 4. Basically, the fracture mechanisms are similar to those of the sandwich panels of KEVLAR. Representative penetrated fracture appearances of sandwich panels of KEVLAR and sandwich panels of Graphite are shown in Fig. 5. Both facesheets of KEVLAR and Graphite show a diamond-shape circumferential fracture and cross-type radial fracture along the two woven fiber directions. No further deformation was seen outside the diamond area. Figs. 6(a) & (b) are the fracture patterns for sandwich panels of Graphite and KEVLAR, respectively. The fracture mechanisms are fiber pull-out and fiber breakage, with very little damage (deformation, cracks) propagated to the neighborhood of the penetrated zone area.

2. Three-Point-Bending Test

As described in the introduction, one distinct feature of composite sandwich panels is the exceptional bending properties. Fig. 7 shows the load-deflection curves of KEVLAR/PVC-45, Gr/PVC-45, and PVC-45. The increase in bending load of the sandwich panels is many fold compared to the core alone. Fig. 8 shows the flexural moduli of KEVLAR/PVC, Gr/PVC, and PVC as functions of core density. In general, the modulus increases with increasing density of the core material. This results further support that composite sandwich panels possess exceptional bending properties. This also explains why the composite sandwich panels are tough compared to the foam core alone.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Composite sandwich panels, each containing only two layers of facesheets of KEVLAR 49 or graphite with epoxy, offer exceptional impact resistance and yet maintain its light-weight characteristics.
2. The impact failure mechanisms of the composite sandwich panels of KEVLAR and Graphite tend to be foam-core-dominated, provided that the PVC foam core possesses a relatively high density.
3. Composite sandwich panels offer excellent flexural properties compared to foam core alone.

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Fig. 5(a)

Fig. 5(b)

Fig. 6(a)

Fig. 6(b)

Fig. 7

Fig. 8